

Metamorphoses in Skin Conductance Response and Pupillary Constriction Based on Gender Stratification

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Abstract

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In the traditional sense, Skin Conductance Response (SCR) can be analysed as a leading indicator of the sympathetic nervous activation that involves stress which is experienced by most computer users. Recent research has found that the Pupil response can also be controlled by the body system known as the Automatic nervous system (ANS) as another important indicator of the sympatric activation of the body response. This paper tries to investigate the techniques for analysing the pupil response readings and the Electro-dermal activity to predict the metamorphoses in synch to the user interaction. The data used is based on a predefined experiment where sixty different young groups of participants interacted with webpage content and their pupil response and EDA was collected synchronously with their interactions with web contents. The result shows that EDA has the highest conductance effect on their affective state than the pupil response and the response state is a static course at latency.

Keywords: Electrodermal activity, Pupil response, Automatic nervous system, Predictive metamorphoses, Affective state, Webpage content.

1 Introduction

In the study of user emotion and affect state, arousal level changes are one of the profound influences on performance which is a constant factor in everyday activities. The different fluctuations in arousal level are been regulated by the autonomic nervous system which is mainly controlled by the parasympathetic and sympathetic systems of the body tissue, this is mostly indexed in the physiological measuring biosensors like the Electrodermal activity (EDA),

a growing number of investigations also use the Pupil response as a modulated autonomic arousal measure for user emotion. Electro-dermal activity is a measurement of a subject's electrical-related potential of the skin and is mostly correlated with the Pupil response; the EDA measure is associated with two different phenomena of the skin that include self-generated potential intrinsic skin kind.

The potential is mostly a consequence that is linked with a dissimilar skin surface layer placed in a proxy that is coupled with the movement of fluid substance. The second phenomenon is the evoked skin potential response referred to as the sympathetic skin response which changes in potential evoked by electrical and magnetic stimulation. Other skin conductance is associated with skin electrical activity which is the most common in the laboratory as a non-invasive measuring response that is related to emotions like stress, excitement, and relaxation depending on the stimuli and study topic. The mechanism uses current and voltage stimulation at a constant level and is low in frequency. An emotion such as excitement produces a corresponding voltage and current that changes over time in response to the physiological state of the person (Figure 1). Some EDA measurements that are subject to electrical excitement type include Skin resistance, Skin conductance, Skin impedance and Skin admittance which measures based on direct constant current and alternating voltage of the input response system.

Figure 1: Dynamic measurement of EDA in a person using electrodes (Courtesy: Google image).

A typical EDA is measured based on skin conductance with a little constant voltage used for excitement and stress sources across the skin electrodes. The skin admittance provides advantages in measurement that are similar to polarised skin electrodes during an EDA reading and this is usually measured in “Siemens” or micro Siemens (μs). In addition, the changes in the electrical conductance of the kin are correlated to sweat gland activity and EDA increased measure is an indicator of increased arousal and cognitive response. There is also a direct correlation in pupil response subject to intense activity. The main physiology behind a typical pupillary response is a regular balance between the parasympathetic nervous system and the sympathetic nervous sys-

tem (Figure 2). The pupil usually constricts when one is stressed and concentrated on particular tasks and dilates in response to a drugged state or mostly in a relaxed mood.

Figure 2: A Pupil response with a regular balance in parasympathetic and sympathetic nervous system.

In the pupillary response during task completion, there is a decrease in constriction or a widening in the middle of the iris due to reduced stimulation of the optical pathway by the pupil based on affective stimulation. The dilation not only responds to intensity in light but also to an emotional response which is sometimes due to graphic images. Very few researchers have focused on leveraging the balance and relationships between EDA and Pupil response measure; the study is mostly limited to investigations based on task-dependent modulations in the physiological indexes. The pupil size is mostly controlled by low-level visual properties such as color, visual contrast and luminance [1, 2, 3, 4]. Eye movement has an influence on the accuracy of the pupil size measurement and distinct patterns made by eye movements can be seen in different conditions that influence the spatial frequency of the pupil responses.

2 Literature Review

The study [5, 6, 7, 8, 9] on the correlation between physiological measures investigates trial-by-trial fluctuations in parasympathetic and sympathetic modulation of the pupil response. The major indexing of the sympathetic and parasympathetic activity on EDA was recorded at a concurrent level with the pupil response. In this process, the emotional face of the stimuli induces arousal fluctuations that are due to evoked emotional arousal which made the participants maintain some centrally controlled fixation during each trial of the presentation with different emotional face stimuli set at low-level visual prop-

erties. Using the common sympathetic nervous control of pupil response and parasympathetic controlled EDA, the study hypothesized that activation of these nervous systems could decrease the pupillary response and also activation of the Pupil response can increase the synchronous EDA readings. And together the predictions of positive correlates of the physiological response (EDA and changes in Pupil size) can reach the optimal response and high rate performance. Moreover, the baseline pupil response and evoked stimulus or task-evoked stimulus for pupil dilation is thought to reveal distinct neural response processes as epochs. These epochs appear before and after face presentations, which are analysed in separate phases;- this is carried out to determine the correlates of both baseline and task-evoked responses.

These experimental studies are conducted to understand the relations and correlations between physiological responses for accurate interpretations of emotional and arousal states. Most studies [10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15] show the dynamics in measured responses where the pupil response decreases before a particular presentation stimuli and these responses are usually observed after the presented stimuli. Many studies have based observation on the initial pupil constriction after central fixation before the stimulus presentation and this has brought some novel findings that there is no good argument to would demonstrate the pupil constriction but there is a consideration that the constriction is associated with the initial central fixation on the engagement of attention. The observed pupil dilation is synchronous to a recent study [16, 17, 18, 19, 20] on presented affected stimuli while control is on low-level properties of the presented stimuli. The relationship between pupil response and EDA before stimuli presented a significant correlation in task-evoked pupillary response to the after-presented stimuli. In conclusion, the pupil response is noted to change independently of changes in luminance on trial-by-trial fluctuation in pupil response which is attributed to variations in arousal level. This also shows that pupil response can be used as an index in parasympathetic and sympathetic response activity for external stimulus presentation.

3 Method

A pre-defined data were collected from an experiment conducted in a private school consisting of sixty participants for both senior and junior students aged between (10-17) years both female and male for each group, consent and consent form approved by the head of department private school and demography (Table 1) of each group is set for record purposes. A total of four different groups were generated from the participants that took part in the study. The presented stimuli were static webpage content from which they got to choose items they liked and items they didn't like. The participant's pupil dilation in synchronous with their Electro-dermal activ-

Figure 3: Synchronous effect in the three most basic components of EDA and pupil response.

ity was collected while they interacted with the webpage static contents for a total of ten seconds.

The experimental study was set in a way that to obtain an approximate synchronous effect there is an opposite and equation physiological reaction of the main source to presented stimuli (Equation 1, Figure 4)).

$$EDA_{signal} + \left[\frac{\overrightarrow{EDA}}{\overleftarrow{PupilS}} \right] + PupilS_{signal}. \quad (1)$$

$$A \frac{d^3 X}{dt^3} + B \frac{d^2 X}{dt^2} + C \frac{dX}{dt} + D \approx A \frac{d^3 P}{dt^3} + B \frac{d^2 P}{dt^2} + C \frac{dP}{dt} + D \quad (2)$$

Where X and P are the EDA and Pupil response input from the participants, $A, B, C,$ and D are the product of external factors that affect the signal propagation on the reaction from participants. The external factors could be room temperature, clap sounds, and distractions to internal body response. The EDA reaction and pupil response is based on Equation 2 and 4, where the subscript x is subject to reaction from skin conductance.

$$X = \int_{j=1}^n A + B(X_x + C)dt \quad (3)$$

$$P = \int_{i=1}^m A + B(P_x + C)dt \quad (4)$$

With m and n as the limit of the time interval for the study, j and i are the initial stages of the interaction time. The latency in response can be calculated using Equation 5. The components are the user attributes derived from the data model of the participants, and their arousal response is classified as "stress" and "relaxation". The half recovery time for relaxation is given in Equation 5.

(a) Older Male Participants's response reading

(b) Older Female Participants's response reading

(c) Younger Male Participants's response reading

(d) Younger Female Participants's response reading

Figure 4: Aggregate of Physiological readings from Gender groups

$$latency = \int_{i=1}^{m+1} P(x)dt \quad (5)$$

$$half_{recovery} = \int_{i=1}^{m+1} \frac{1}{2} Amp(x)dt \quad (6)$$

The Amplitude response (*Amp*) is the same for both the EDA and Pupil response. The different amplitude values can only be determined by the units of the sensors used in measurement which is also set as constant and falls under the external factors of the physiological recordings (Figure 5).

4 Result

An aggregate of the response readings (Figure 5) from the participants was computed and used for analysis. Figure 5 shows the performance metrics between EDA and Pupil response for the first older male gender group. The comparison is slight and based on $\frac{count}{100}$ error rate, the EDA response has a 60% rate of performance compared to the 75% of the pupil response from the participants. For male pupil response in the older gender, the pupil response is more reactive to external visual stimuli than their EDA response and this serves as an indicator that the eyes contain more arousal effect than the EDA for males. The baseline effect shows that the EDA has less response than the Pupil response with an 85% performance compared to the 80% of the EDA response

measure.

Figure 5: Performance metrics for older male gender group.

Figure 7 shows the performance measure of EDA and pupil response for the Female gender participants and the EDA response effect is more reactive than the pupil response with the performance of 68% and 55%. The skin conductance level (Baseline) also indicates a 0.1% error in pupil response to 0.5% error in EDA response. It is known [21, 22, 23, 24, 25] that female pupils respond by dilating more in a relaxed mood to external stimuli which is caused by their perception of the clarity of the stimulus, there is a significant positive correlation between the perceived beauty of the stimuli they viewed. The positive response is usually associated with attractiveness that is premised on the constant existence of the unconscious perception and the physical response when compared to their EDA response.

Figure 6: Aggregate performance metrics for Arousal states.

Figure 7: Performance metrics for older female gender group.

Figure 8 indicates the response metrics on the younger male gender group (aged between 8-10 years), their physiological response usually seems to be more reactive and hyperactive due to their enthusiasm. The realistic accommodative pupil response is shown to be present in the younger male group for children but is usually weaker when compared to the older male group above (Figure 5). The different levels of vivid web content lead to minor and additive differences between the older and younger male group. The EDA response for this group has a 70% reactive performance as compared to the 73% reactive performance in their pupil response. The baseline metric margin also shows a distinct difference in reactive level. The EDA is more reactive than its pupil response.

Table 1: Demography of participants on different groups.

Participant's age group	Gender score	Eye condition	Consent
7-10	10.5	Normal	Approved
11-13	9	Normal	Approved
14-17	10.1	Normal	Approved

Figure 9 shows the reactive performance in the physiological response of the younger female gender, in this group, it can be noted that the physiological clarification that can be placed in pupil and EDA response is that the normal pupil constriction is set at a balanced state between the sympathetic and parasympathetic nervous systems. EDA amplitude is seen to be correlated with it and the baseline pupil response; the sympathetic innervation leads to the pupil dilation controlled by dilator muscle and corresponds to active spikes in EDA readings for female children and hence stress and confused mood are in the lesser list of classified emotional response

Figure 8: Performance metrics for younger male gender group.

Figure 9: Performance metrics for younger female gender group.

(Table 2). There is an almost equal performance rate in both EDA and pupillary response in reaction to vivid web contents placed in front of them. The reaction can also be due to over-excitement and external factors and anomalies can also be multiple and indecisive in conclusion and stress mood seem to be the most reactive arousal state for all group of participants (Figure 6).

Table 2: Confusion matrix on test performance.

	Stress mood	Relaxed mood	Confused mood
Stressed mood	10	16	8
Relaxed mood	10	20	10
Confused mood	9	24	5

5 Conclusion

This paper aims to investigate and analyse the predictive metamorphoses in EDA and Pupillary measures on younger gender stratification, the data used is based on a predefined experiment where sixty different groups of participants interacted with webpage content, and their pupil response and EDA were collected synchronously to their interactions with the web contents. The result shows that EDA has the highest conductance effect on their affective state than the pupil response in younger participants than the older participants; this response effect shows that the parasympathetic nervous system is reactive to vivid and well-pleasing external stimulus based on the pupil response control muscle. The study of

pupil response in both adult and young groups should be into future investigations on the effects of physiological response to stimulus as one of the indicators of arousal state. The components should to set and simulated close to the EDA response components. Future perception of the work would be to compare the pupil response effect with that of the heart rate readings given these physiological measures have similar and reactive response effects; the process would be carried out as analytics for physiological measures for both adult and younger participants.

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